

Classroom Social Dynamics and Supportive Learning Environment in Public Elementary Schools

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ABSTRACT: Public elementary schools are currently dealing with variety of classroom concerns such as pupils' academic difficulties, behavioral issues, social problems, and emotional difficulties. These can be resolved by providing an environment supportive to learning in classroom social dynamics. These dynamics pertain to how students, teachers, and the learning environment interact and relate to one another. These may be affected by teachers' influence and social influence. A descriptive-correlational type of research was used in this study to describe the relationship of supportive learning environment and classroom social dynamics as to teachers' influence and social influence with 115 Grade Six pupil-respondents in five public elementary schools in San Antonio District in academic year 2022-2023. The research made-survey questionnaire was used for gathering data with some concepts adapted and modified. Pearson-Product-Moment-Correlation-Coefficient revealed that social influence in terms of conformity, expectation, compliance and obedience is significantly related to supportive learning environment as to pupils' academic performance, engagement, self-regulation and self-resiliency. Likewise, teachers' influence in terms of referent, expert and reward were also found significantly related to supportive learning environment. However, teachers' legitimate influence was found to be significantly related to pupils' engagement and self-regulation only, while teachers' coercive influence was found out to have no relationship with a supportive learning environment.

KEYWORDS: classroom social dynamics, social influence, supportive learning environment, teachers' influence

INTRODUCTION

Students and teachers interact, connect and collaborate with one another in a school culture where optimal learning and the drive to learn is encouraged, appreciated and acknowledged. This type of setting fosters students' growth and appreciation of learning, which results in improved academic achievement. These interactions between students, teachers, and the learning environment, as well as how these elements impact learning, is referred to as classroom social dynamics. Classroom social dynamics are influenced by two key elements: teachers' influence and social influence. The authority and impact that teachers have on their students is referred to as their influence. Many factors, such as teachers' education, skill, and experience, might have an impact to students. On the other hand, social influence is the influence that other people in a student's life, such as parents, family members, classmates, and/or peers, have on one another. In a classroom setting, social influence can come from the interactions and relationships between students.

Students in the process of socialization need a healthy environment and models in order to perform better (Usman & Madudili, 2019). Teachers' and social influences are both vital to creating such a healthy learning environment. According to Becton (2017), productive learning environments are essential for students' intellectual, emotional, and social success in school. It takes effort and planning to create a learning environment that is conducive to learning. The Department of Education also stated in its goal that it wanted to support every Filipino's access to an education where children may learn in a safe and motivating environment and schools can create a supportive environment for optimal learning.

Moreover, public elementary schools including San Antonio District are currently dealing with variety of concerns, particularly in the classroom, such as pupils' academic difficulties, behavioral issues, social problems, and emotional difficulties. Most pupils are struggling in performing and engaging academically wherein they are frequently having problems in participating actively in activities, getting low scores in assessments, disengaged and unmotivated to learn, and being distracted and unfocused in class. Some also displays disruptive behavior, not obeying classroom rules and standards, and even exhibiting low self-control and self-esteem in expressing their ideas in the class, accomplishing assigned tasks, and collaborating with other pupils. These matters can influence their academic development, social relationships and overall well-being. These concerns can be resolved by providing an environment supportive to learning. Teachers and other people around the learners can provide this support system.

Thus, the main objective of this study is to determine the relationship of classroom social dynamics and supportive learning environment in Public Elementary Schools. This study is rooted on the belief that the classroom is not only a place of instruction,

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but also a social environment that influences students' learning experiences. Specifically, it intends to describe classroom social dynamics as to teachers' influence in terms of legitimate, referent, expert, reward and coercive as perceived by the respondents. This also aims to determine the perception of the respondents on the observed social influence as to conformity, expectation, compliance and obedience. It also aims to determine the extent of the respondents perceived supportive learning environment manifested as to their academic performance, engagement, self-regulation and self-resiliency. Further, the study aims to determine whether a significant relationship exists between supportive learning environment and classroom social dynamics as to teachers' influence and social influence.

METHODOLOGY

A. Research Design

Descriptive-correlational type of research was used in the study to determine the relationship between classroom social dynamics as to teachers' influence and social influence, the independent variables, and supportive learning environment, the dependent variables.

Jones (2021), claimed that descriptive study design aims to observe and describe a subject's or phenomenon's activity without interfering. Whereas correlational research is a type of research design that looks at the relationships between two or more variables (Cherry, 2022).

B. Respondents of the Study

The respondents of the study were 115 Grade Six pupils from five public elementary schools in San Antonio District, Division of Quezon, namely Callejon Elementary School, Briones ES, Sintorisan ES, Magsaysay ES, and Del Valle ES, which all belong to the second zone of the said district. The researcher used purposive sampling technique. The questionnaire was pre-tested using 30 Grade Six pupils from other school which are not respondents of the study to determine the reliability and validity of the instrument.

C. Instrumentation and Data Collection

A researcher-made survey questionnaire was used for gathering data with some concepts adapted and modified. This was validated by panel of experts and validators including two Master Teachers, two Teacher-III, a Teacher-II, and the District Research Coordinator, who were additionally requested to review the survey instrument's validity, content and language. The questionnaire also underwent reliability tests using Cronbach Alpha. Items that were determined to be weak were revised and modified to develop the final copy of the questionnaires. The researcher personally distributed the questionnaires to the pupil-respondents and gathered the data with the approval of the Superintendent, District Supervisor, and School Heads.

D. Data Analysis

The collected data were analyzed using a suitable statistical treatment for the study. The findings were interpreted to answer the questions and meet the study's goal. The result of the 90 item questions collected in the survey questionnaire were treated confidentially and were used only for the study.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents the results of the study, the analyses and interpretations of the gathered data.

Table 1. Mean Perception of the Respondents to the Classroom Social Dynamics as to Teachers' Influence in terms of Legitimate

Indicators	Mean	SD	Interpretation
My teacher...			
1. requires us to follow his/her rules.	4.77	0.43	Highly Observed
2. expects us to behave at all times.	4.77	0.47	Highly Observed
3. tells us our duties in the classroom.	4.78	0.41	Highly Observed
4. has the complete and total control of the classroom.	4.68	0.49	Highly Observed
5. has the final decision inside the classroom.	4.58	0.56	Highly Observed
6. has the right to decide what we will study and what tasks we are going to do.	4.88	0.35	Highly Observed
7. instructs us to study hard and be obedient in order to pass.	4.81	0.42	Highly Observed
Overall	4.75	0.29	Highly Observed

Legend: 4.50-5.0-Strongly Agree/ Highly Observed

3.50-4.49-Agree/ Observed

2.50-3.49- Moderately Agree/ Moderately Observed

1.50-2.49-Disagree/ Slightly Observed

1.00-1.49-Strongly Disagree/ Not Observed

Table 1 displays that indicator 6, "My teacher has the right to decide what we will study and what tasks we are going to do" has the highest mean of 4.88 and verbal interpretation of strongly agree among the indicators on legitimate influence. It shows that the

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pupil-respondents “highly observed” that their teachers, as part of their duties, have the right to decide on their learning experiences and curriculum. Teachers set standards and expectations in the class by providing pupils the target lessons and the allotted time in teaching the necessary competencies. At the start of every lesson, teachers also nowadays are suggested to tell the class what are expected of them to learn at the end of the lesson. By doing so, there will be clear learning goals and objectives for the students. When teachers establish these routines that are consistent and focused on learning outcomes, students may develop trust for their teachers’ actions and decisions. This contribute to the students' perception that their teachers are in charge of delivering instruction to them, thus, have the right to choose appropriate study materials and learning opportunities for them.

Meanwhile indicator 5, “My teacher has the final decision inside the classroom” got the lowest mean of 4.58 among the ten indicators, but then, it is also interpreted as strongly agree. The findings imply that pupils “highly observed” that their teachers are authority figures in making ultimate decisions in the classroom. They decide on seating arrangements, classroom rules and organizations, activities and/or performance tasks to do, schedule of submission of outputs, and the like. In these various situations in the classroom, teachers may involve the students in decision-making process by allowing them to give their views, ideas and suggestions. Different viewpoints could arise, but then, teachers have the final say on those matters.

The given table also reveals that the overall mean of 4.75 and standard deviation of 0.29 indicates that the pupil-respondents strongly agree to all of the indicators. It shows that the respondents perceived the classroom social dynamics is “highly observed” as to legitimate influence. This means that the pupils viewed that their teachers set standards and expectations in the classroom by constantly reminding the pupils what are required and expected of them to do. They instruct them the classroom rules and routines as well as the assigned duties and tasks in order to establish rules and guidelines. Teachers, as having the position of authority, pupils seen them to have the right to organize, control and decide on the matters in their classroom.

The study result is supported by Cummings (2017) that the students’ acceptance of the teacher's authority to demand the modified behavior and their need to comply is what gave rise to teachers’ legitimate influence. It demonstrates how interactions within the classroom are influenced by the teachers' influence of position toward the students.

Table 2. Mean Perception of the Respondents to the Classroom Social Dynamics as to Teachers’ Influence in terms of Referent

Indicators	Mean	SD	Interpretation
My teacher...			
1. is approachable and respectable.	4.71	0.45	Highly Observed
2. is sincere and genuine with us.	4.77	0.48	Highly Observed
3. is open, fair and honest with pupils.	4.74	0.53	Highly Observed
4. is concern for our future.	4.79	0.47	Highly Observed
5. is admirable in which pupils wish to be like him/her.	4.65	0.61	Highly Observed
6. has an attractive personality.	4.50	0.74	Highly Observed
7. cares about us every day.	4.72	0.54	Highly Observed
8. is both an inspiration and a role model for us.	4.69	0.61	Highly Observed
Overall	4.70	0.40	Highly Observed

Legend: 4.50-5.0-Strongly Agree/ Highly Observed

3.50-4.49-Agree/ Observed

2.50-3.49- Moderately Agree/ Moderately Observed

1.50-2.49-Disagree/ Slightly Observed

1.00-1.49-Strongly Disagree/ Not Observed

Table 2 displays that among the indicators of referent influence of teachers, indicator 4, “My teacher is concern for our future” is the indicator which noted to have the highest mean of 4.79 and is interpreted as strongly agree. This implies that pupils “highly observed” that their teachers behave in various ways to show that they care about their students' futures. One of these is when teachers provide personalized attention, feedback and instruction such as extending time for enrichment and remedial classes. Teachers provide enrichment activities to those advanced-level pupils to develop their knowledge and skills better. On the other hand, teachers also provide remediation or intervention activities to struggling pupils or those pupils who temporarily fallen behind in their studies and otherwise need additional support in their learning. They may also offer advice, career counseling, and help students set academic and personal goals. Pupils may also perceive that their teachers remind them to study hard and behave well in order for them to use it in real-life and in the future.

Meanwhile, indicator 6, “My teacher has an attractive personality” got the lowest mean of 4.50 and is also interpreted as strongly agree, which may imply that the pupils “highly observed” that their teacher is likeable and has a pleasant disposition. Students strongly perceived that their teachers reflect traits and behaviors that appeal to them, such as when they teach joyfully, excitedly and enthusiastically. They can also demonstrate empathy and understanding by being understanding, kind, and responsive to the individual needs and challenges of their students. Additionally, teachers may show sense of humor, listen to students'

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perspectives, offer helpful criticism, and treat their students fairly, which can influence pupils to admire their teachers' characteristics.

On the whole, Table 2 shows that all the respondents strongly agree in all the 8 item indicators above, given the overall mean of 4.70 with standard deviation of 0.40. The result implies that the respondents perceived that the classroom social dynamics is "highly observed" as to referent influence. This shows that teachers demonstrate qualities that attract or appeal to the pupils. Teachers set a good example for students by acting with kindness, fairness, empathy, and honesty. They put time and effort into developing meaningful connections with their students. They genuinely care about their students' life, listen to their concerns, and support them emotionally. They may also share their personal stories that can inspire pupils. By encouraging students' voice or empowering students to speak up and share their ideas and concerns, they can also create open channels for communication with their pupils. They encourage student participation while carefully listening to their students' viewpoints and offering helpful criticism. In class discussions, group projects, and other activities, students may have the chance to express their thoughts, opinions, questions and experiences. These matters align with DepEd Order 36, s.2013, or the Department of Education's aim to promote education in which pupils learn in a child-friendly and motivating environment. Teachers' referent influence may help to facilitate this learning.

According to Hawamdeh (2013), referent influence strengthens the teacher-student relationship, resulting in admiration for the teacher. When pupils admire the teacher, the teacher's statements will be most appreciated by the students, who will then do everything in their ability not to displease him/her and act responsibly and appropriately. When a teacher is well-liked by the students, they are more likely to follow directions and avoid upsetting them.

Table 3. Mean Perception of the Respondents to the Classroom Social Dynamics as to Teachers' Influence in terms of Expert

Indicators	Mean	SD	Interpretation
My teacher...			
1. clearly organizes and teaches lessons.	4.85	0.40	Highly Observed
2. is knowledgeable and competent in teaching.	4.84	0.41	Highly Observed
3. is skillful in managing the class.	4.73	0.50	Highly Observed
4. uses techniques in teaching that helps us better understand the lesson.	4.76	0.56	Highly Observed
5. provides us what we need that suited to our interests and abilities.	4.57	0.61	Highly Observed
6. asks questions that develop our higher order thinking skills.	4.61	0.59	Highly Observed
7. gives us assessment that can improve our learnings about the lesson.	4.72	0.45	Highly Observed
Overall	4.73	0.35	Highly Observed

Legend: 4.50-5.0-Strongly Agree/ Highly Observed

3.50-4.49-Agree/ Observed

2.50-3.49- Moderately Agree/ Moderately Observed

1.50-2.49-Disagree/ Slightly Observed

1.00-1.49-Strongly Disagree/ Not Observed

Presented in Table 3 were the perception of the pupil-respondents on expert influence of teachers. It shows that indicator 1 which states that "My teacher clearly organizes and teaches lessons" has the highest mean of 4.85 and has verbal interpretation of strongly agree. This implies that the pupil-respondents "highly observed" that their teachers are expert in the subject that they are teaching. Teachers show competence and knowledge on structuring and delivering educational content in a way that is easy for the students to understand and follow. Teachers execute their crafted lesson plans by utilizing strategies and approaches as well as designing engaging activities and assessments, necessary for the attainment of the lesson objectives. Teachers may also incorporate the use of appropriate instructional materials such as the ICT based materials as well as contextualized, localized and indigenized materials which are strongly suggested to use by DepEd nowadays. In these manners, students were able to clearly see how their teachers planned and delivered classes to them.

Table 3 also reveals the lowest mean of 4.57 which is indicator 5, "My teacher provides us what we need that suited to our interests and abilities". It suggests that the pupils "highly observed" that their teachers are providing them with engaging lessons and activities that suited to them and would enhance their learning and potential. Teachers execute differentiated instruction by providing individual or group learning experiences that cater diverse learning needs and abilities of each pupil. As one of the pedagogical approaches recommended by Policy Guidelines on the K to 12 Basic Education Program (DO No. 021, s. 2019), differentiation takes into consideration the varied learning styles and multiple intelligences of the learners, which are important facets of their individual diversity. Teachers may reflect expertise in adjusting the learning experience to each student's particular interests and aptitudes.

Moreover, an overall mean of 4.73 with standard deviation of 0.35 was also displayed on the table. This shows that the respondents perceived that the classroom social dynamics is "highly observed" as to expert influence. It implies that pupils strongly perceived that their teachers exhibit knowledge, skills and competence in teaching and managing the class. Teachers utilize approaches, strategies and techniques in teaching and provide learning opportunities suitable for learners. It is in consonance with

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DO No.42, s. 2017 or National Adoption and Implementation of the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers wherein teachers should possess mastery of content knowledge and pedagogy and ability to establish learning environments that are responsive to learner diversity. If pupils perceived their teachers' expertise in this field, it has the potential to influence how students interact with their teachers. Students are more inclined to comply with a teacher's directions and guidance if they regard the teacher as experts.

According to Thomas (2014), a teacher's knowledge and experience are mirrored in the classroom by his/her expert influence. Students may not want to follow a teacher who does not know what he or she is doing. The point is that a teacher must know his/her stuff and be able to communicate it confidently and clearly to the students.

Table 4. Mean Perception of the Respondents to the Classroom Social Dynamics as to Teachers' Influence in terms of Reward

Indicators	Mean	SD	Interpretation
My teacher...			
1. recognizes our effort in completing assigned tasks.	4.68	0.60	Highly Observed
2. gives prizes as rewards to encourage good work or performance.	4.22	0.94	Observed
3. appreciates when we review or study our lessons.	4.68	0.67	Highly Observed
4. commends or praises us when we actively participate in class discussion.	4.58	0.75	Highly Observed
5. gives us compliments or praises when we obey or follow his/her instructions.	4.50	0.78	Highly Observed
6. gives award or prize when pupils pass quizzes, tests or other assessment.	4.49	0.64	Observed
7. is consistent in giving rewards to pupils.	4.02	1.00	Observed
Overall	4.45	0.57	Observed

Legend: 4.50-5.0-Strongly Agree/ Highly Observed

3.50-4.49-Agree/ Observed

2.50-3.49- Moderately Agree/ Moderately Observed

1.50-2.49-Disagree/ Slightly Observed

1.00-1.49-Strongly Disagree/ Not Observed

Table 4 presents that indicators 1 and 3 which state that "My teacher recognizes our effort in completing assigned tasks" and "My teacher appreciates when we review or study our lessons" both got the highest mean of 4.68 and verbal interpretation of strongly agree. This implies that both of these indicators were "highly observed" by the pupil-respondents. In indicator 1, it shows that their teachers demonstrate appreciation and recognition of pupils' effort in finishing their academic obligations. On the other hand, in indicator 3, it indicates that the respondents clearly seen that their teacher appreciates and supports their effort in reviewing and studying as essential components of the learning process. Both statements show that the students perceive that their teacher values their efforts, recognizes their dedication, and supports their learning journey. Pupils perceive these matters when teachers compliment or praise and acknowledge their effort in their studies. Teachers may also exhibit rewarding students for their exemplary academic behavior with prizes or rewards like extra credit or bonus points, ribbons, small tokens, applause, and the like.

Meanwhile, indicator 7, "My teacher is consistent in giving rewards to pupils" got the lowest mean of 4.02 with verbal interpretation of agree. This shows that pupils "observed" that their teachers constantly give rewards to pupils. Teachers provide prizes, awards, praises, recognition to pupils who meet their standards and academically and behaviorally. In doing this, teachers openly communicate the expectations and criteria for earning these rewards and students can see that these guidelines are consistently followed, thus, they view the rewards as being given consistently.

As can also be gleaned in the table, the overall mean is 4.45 with 0.57 overall standard deviation. This indicates that the teachers' reward influence is "observed" by the respondents in the classroom social dynamics. Teachers give either verbal praises, certificates, extra credits, or classroom privileges such as allowing a student to choose their seat, be a classroom helper, extending break time for leisure or going out early, which are all in exchange for pupils' academic accomplishments or improvements and good behavior. Teachers are often using rewards to motivate and encourage pupils to obey on their rules and do well at school. This might be helpful for pupils to make them feel that what they do is being recognized and appreciated.

According to Fitriati, et.al. (2020), it was vital to provide pupils with positive reinforcement. In order to reduce unfavorable consequences and boost teacher-student interaction, rewarding of pupils should be fairly done. Thus, through the use of rewards to influence student conduct and attitudes, teachers can significantly affect the social dynamics in the classroom. Teachers employ reward schemes to encourage their students and promote positive behavior. Teachers can promote cooperation and active learning in their students by doing this.

Table 5. Mean Perception of the Respondents to the Classroom Social Dynamics as to Teachers' Influence in terms of Coercive

Indicators	Mean	SD	Interpretation
My teacher...			
1. threatens to fail pupils who do not follow his/her instructions.	2.09	1.32	Slightly Observed

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2. stares and yell at students who misbehave in class.	2.13	1.35	Slightly Observed
3. embarrasses pupils who do not perform well in class.	1.63	1.06	Slightly Observed
4. scolds pupils who are not listening in class discussion.	2.88	1.35	Moderately Observed
5. punishes talkative pupils during class.	2.08	1.19	Slightly Observed
6. gets angry to pupils who do not cooperate in activities.	3.21	1.23	Moderately Observed
7. shouts at pupils who do not have assignments or home works.	1.77	1.12	Slightly Observed
Overall	2.25	0.85	Slightly Observed

Legend: 4.50-5.0-Strongly Agree/ Highly Observed

3.50-4.49-Agree/ Observed

2.50-3.49- Moderately Agree/ Moderately Observed

1.50-2.49-Disagree/ Slightly Observed

1.00-1.49-Strongly Disagree/ Not Observed

Table 5 shows the perception of pupil-respondents on teachers' influence with regards to coercive. Indicator 6, "My teacher gets angry to pupils who do not cooperate in activities" got the highest mean of 3.21 and interpreted as moderately agree by pupils. It shows that the pupil-respondents "moderately observed" that their teacher gets mad to uncooperative pupils. It means that the teacher sometimes becomes unhappy with students who are unwilling or resistant in participating or working together in various activities or tasks. Teachers frequently design exercises and activities to encourage participation, cooperation, and learning among their pupils. The effectiveness of these events depends on student cooperation and active involvement. However, when certain students decide not to collaborate, it can interfere with the lesson's flow, impede learning, and may foster hostile social dynamics. Findings showed that the respondents may perceived that even though their teachers may sometimes demonstrate their displeasure with the pupils who are not actively participating in the activities as expected or contributing in any other way, this is just to discipline them and for them to be aware that their actions are inappropriate. The teacher's goal is typically to inspire disobedient pupils to participate in class, work together, and uphold their obligations as members of the learning community. It just depends on the pupils' perception on how they will treat this disciplining technique towards them.

On the other hand, the indicator which got the lowest mean of 1.63 is indicator 3 which states that "My teacher embarrasses pupils who do not perform well in class". It shows that the pupil-respondents disagree that their teacher shame pupils who struggles in class. This suggests that pupils might perceive that their teachers provide them classroom environment which is supportive and respectful, where mistakes are seen as learning opportunities, rather than sources of shame. The pupils may feel that their teachers employ a different approach to addressing academic difficulties, such as providing constructive feedback, offering additional support, or using positive reinforcement instead of publicly embarrassing students. Teachers may always advise their students to participate as much as they can in class and not be afraid to give incorrect answers, make errors, or fail because these things can be fixed, and what matters is that they make an effort to do their best when answering questions and completing tasks. With these, pupils are not afraid to ask questions, to share their ideas and concerns openly, and to make mistakes in the classroom dynamics.

Furthermore, the table shows the overall mean of 2.25 with standard deviation of 0.85 and verbal interpretation of disagree. It shows that the respondents perceived that the classroom social dynamics is "slightly observed" as to coercive influence. It means that the pupils do not feel and perceive their social interactions within the classroom involve manipulative practices that may limit their freedom. This disagreement suggests that the pupils view the classroom as a space where their voices and opinions are respected. If students do anything that does not satisfy the standards and expectations of the teacher, the teacher does not usually utilize unfavorable consequences and punishments. If teachers reprimand students for misconduct sometimes, they may follow up by explaining to pupils that they are only doing so for disciplinary reasons. With these, pupils may feel that their contributions are valued and that they have the autonomy to express themselves without fear of negative consequences or undue pressure in the social dynamics in the classroom.

As supported by Alderman and Green (2021), it states that teachers must use coercive influence in the least upsetting way possible because this base approach may be harmful. While it is important for students to understand boundaries and standards, they should not regard such authority as a threat to their own need for personal control.

Table 6. Summary of Mean Perception of the Respondents to the Classroom Social Dynamics as to Teachers' Influence

Teachers' Influence	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Legitimate	4.75	0.29	Highly Observed
Referent	4.70	0.40	Highly Observed
Expert	4.73	0.35	Highly Observed
Reward	4.45	0.57	Observed
Coercive	2.25	0.85	Slightly Observed
Overall	4.18	0.49	Observed

Legend: 4.50-5.0-Strongly Agree/ Highly Observed

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- 3.50-4.49-Agree/ Observed
- 2.50-3.49- Moderately Agree/ Moderately Observed
- 1.50-2.49-Disagree/ Slightly Observed
- 1.00-1.49-Strongly Disagree/ Not Observed

Table 6 summarizes the weighted mean distribution on the responses on the classroom social dynamics as to teachers' influence. Having the highest mean of 4.75 and interpreted as "strongly agree", it implies that legitimate as teachers' influence is "highly observed" in classroom social dynamics. It demonstrates that teachers are always exerting classroom control by its position authority and it is undeniably perceived by their pupils which can be utilized to impose rules and uphold discipline in interactions and relationships within the classroom. Teachers set standards and expectations and establish rules and guidelines for behavior in the classroom in which pupils try to meet. Likewise, the table also shows that teachers' expert influence is "highly observed" in the classroom social dynamics. Pupils perceived that their teachers are competent and knowledgeable in teaching lessons and providing necessary teaching techniques, instructional materials and learning opportunities to them. Students might be more inclined to trust and appreciate their teachers' authority when they observe and believe that they are well-organized and informed. Teachers' referent influence is also "highly observed" by the pupils in the classroom social dynamics. Pupils may clearly see that their teachers are caring, sincere, approachable as well as a model who inspires them. Moreover, teachers' reward influence is "observed" in the classroom wherein pupils perceived that their teachers are frequently using rewards to motivate and encourage good performance and behavior among pupils. On the other hand, coercive influence got the lowest mean of 2.25, interpreted as "Disagree". This means that coercive influence practices are "slightly observed" by the pupils. This shows that teachers are rarely using this influence in classroom interactions for they are aware that although using the threat of punishment or negative consequences to induce students to comply can be useful in some instances, it is not always the ideal option. The main reason behind utilizing teachers' coercive influence to some extent is not to degrade but to uphold student discipline.

Furthermore, an overall mean of 4.18 and standard deviation of 0.49 with a verbal interpretation of "Agree" is also shown in the table. It implies that the pupil-respondents "observed" these influences of their teachers in classroom social dynamics. Pupils perceived and noticed how teachers interact with students, how they assert their control, how they provide motivation and encouragement, or how they establish their expertise. These observations influence the students' perception of the teacher's role and their willingness to comply with their instructions. Pupils' observations can shed light on the teacher-student relationship dynamics within the classroom. They may notice how teachers engage with students, whether they are approachable, supportive, assertive, or create an inclusive learning environment. These observations can affect the students' level of comfort, trust, and motivation to engage in the learning process. Teachers' actions, attitudes, and skills can also shape the social interactions and behaviors of the students within the classroom. The connections between pupils can be influenced by teachers.

The study was supported by Anagaw and Mossu (2019) that the type of influence base used by teachers, how students perceive it, and how it influences learner interactions are all important. Students' views of the teachers' influence base may impact their behavior and interactions with their peers. Positive student behaviors are more likely to be promoted by teachers who use a positive and collaborative influence foundation.

Table 7. Mean Perception of the Respondents to the Classroom Social Dynamics as to Social Influence in terms of Conformity

Indicators	Mean	SD	Interpretation
As a pupil, I...			
1. express my ideas or opinions in class the same way that my other active classmates do.	4.26	0.82	Practiced
2. take down and review my notes to imitate the honor students in the class.	4.32	0.83	Practiced
3. raise my hand to participate in the discussion, just like my friends do in the class.	4.49	0.68	Practiced
4. practice reading and mathematics to improve my skills because my peers or friends do the same.	4.53	0.63	Highly Practiced
5. copy other pupils in joining school contests or classroom-based activities.	4.07	1.08	Practiced
6. follow my teacher's instructions like the other students.	4.55	0.60	Highly Practiced
7. greet politely and/ or bless to the teachers as the other students do.	4.49	0.64	Practiced
Overall	4.39	0.46	Practiced

Legend: 4.50-5.0-Strongly Agree/ Highly Practiced

3.50-4.49-Agree/ Practiced

2.50-3.49- Moderately Agree/ Moderately Practiced

1.50-2.49-Disagree/ Slightly Practiced

1.00-1.49-Strongly Disagree/ Not Practiced

Table 7 displays the perception of the respondents to the classroom social dynamics as to social influence in terms of conformity. Indicator 6, "As a pupil, I follow my teacher's instructions like the other students" got the highest mean of 4.55. It may imply that the pupil-respondents "highly practiced" conforming other pupils in obeying their teacher. They may want to blend in with the class'

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norms rather than stick out or disrupt the status quo. Because they observe their peers or other students doing the same things, they may be more willing to follow their teacher's instructions in situations like maintaining silence, cleaning the designated areas, possessing good qualities, adhering to the directions in answering and completing the tasks, and the like.

Meanwhile, it can also be gleaned from the table the lowest mean of 4.07 which is indicator 5 which states that "As a pupil, I copy other pupils in joining school contests or classroom-based activities". It may indicate that pupils "practiced" participating in contests or activities as influenced by other pupils. When pupils copy other pupils in joining activities, they are either conforming to the group norms or imitating other people that they look up to. Schools usually held contests or activities either school-based or classroom-based such as beauty contests, art, reading and numeracy activities, sports activities, and the like. Students may be encouraged to join in these activities if they see their peers, classmates, or other students who have influence over them doing so.

It shows the overall mean rating of 4.39 and standard deviation of 0.46 with verbal interpretation of Agree. This indicates that the social influence in terms of conformity is "practiced" by the learners. Due to societal standards and norms, there is a degree of conformity in the classroom where students often adjust their personalities to emulate and fit into the standards set by their peers or teacher. They may participate in the class, study lessons, practice reading and numeracy during free time, clean the classroom and assigned areas, and/or explore their skills or talents, as influenced by their classmates or peers.

According to the study of McGuigan and Stevenson (2016) that children are not uniformly conformists, but rather respond selectively based on the features of the group majority. This means that while children are not always conformists, they are more inclined to do so when they believe that the majority of their peer group is coherent, reliable, and deserving of respect. When children desire to fit in, be accepted, and avoid rejection, they often adopt the attitudes and behaviors of their peers. However, depending on their personality features, temperament, and prior experiences, they also differ personally in their tendency to conform. These matters may affect the interactions and relationships within the classroom.

Table 8. Mean Perception of the Respondents to the Classroom Social Dynamics as to Social Influence in terms of Expectation

Indicators	Mean	SD	Interpretation
As a pupil, I...			
1. focus in class just as a student should.	4.56	0.58	Highly Practiced
2. follow classroom rules as expected to me as an intermediate pupil.	4.50	0.68	Highly Practiced
3. follow my teacher's instructions in doing class works just what I should do as a responsible student.	4.74	0.55	Highly Practiced
4. respect everyone in the class just as a disciplined student should.	4.51	0.74	Highly Practiced
5. cooperate in cleaning our assigned area as a member of the school.	4.57	0.61	Highly Practiced
6. keep silent during school programs or activities as expected of me as a role model as a grade six student.	4.17	0.84	Practiced
7. make myself look clean and presentable as would be expected of me as a male/female.	4.45	0.67	Practiced
Overall	4.50	0.45	Highly Practiced

Legend: 4.50-5.0-Strongly Agree/ Highly Practiced

3.50-4.49-Agree/ Practiced

2.50-3.49- Moderately Agree/ Moderately Practiced

1.50-2.49-Disagree/ Slightly Practiced

1.00-1.49-Strongly Disagree/ Not Practiced

Displayed in Table 8 is indicator 3 with the highest mean of 4.74 which states that "As a pupil, I follow my teacher's instructions in doing class works just what I should do as a responsible student" shows that the pupil-respondents "highly practiced" this in the classroom social dynamics. Pupils may demonstrate following teachers' instructions by completing the assigned class works according to the given directions, take responsibility for their work, meeting the deadlines, following the guidelines and meeting the desired standards set and provided by the teachers. This suggests that the pupils understand that as a student, it is important to follow the teacher's instructions when doing class works, and that doing so is part of their responsibility of being a good student. This may reflect the social expectations placed on students to behave in a certain way, including following instructions from authority figures such as teachers. The use of the phrase 'just as I should do' suggests a sense of obligation or duty to follow these expectations and behave responsibly in the classroom.

On the other hand, indicator 6 with the lowest mean of 4.17 states that "As a pupil, I keep silent during school programs or activities as expected of me as a role model as a grade six student" may imply that the pupils "practiced" this because of the social expectations to them as role models as grade six students, thus, understand that it is expected of them to remain silent during school programs or activities. The pupils acknowledge that they are a role model to other students and as such, they have a social expectation and responsibility to demonstrate good behavior and follow the rules set by their school. Schools usually held events either school-based or classroom-based such as Nutrition Month, Buwan ng Wika, Reading Month, Art Month, International Day of Mathematics,

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and many more, which have various activities. By keeping silent, the pupils are showing respect for the activity or program, and setting an example for others to follow.

On the whole, the respondents' perception to the classroom social dynamics as to social influence in terms of expectation has an overall mean rating of 4.50 and overall standard deviation of 0.45. It displays that the pupil-respondents "strongly agree" that they do things as expected by other people which reflects that social influence is "highly practiced" by the pupils. Social influence may play a role in shaping classroom social dynamics, particularly through the influence of expectations. It often leads individuals to behave due to what is expected of them brought about by their social roles. Students may conform to the expectations set by their peers, teachers, or the overall classroom culture. This may impact the behavior and attitudes of students, as they may behave to what is considered acceptable or desirable within the group. Students tend to follow rules and instructions, be presentable, study hard and/or possess good conduct due to the expectations of them by their social roles as sixth-grade pupil, a responsible and disciplined intermediate level pupil, a male or female, and the like.

Likewise, Drew (2022) explained that individuals' social roles are determined by their social status. Social roles and social status play an important role in shaping individuals' behavior and expectations. These roles and status may have a set of social duties and be expected to behave as set by the roles they play.

Table 9. Mean Perception of the Respondents to the Classroom Social Dynamics as to Social Influence in terms of Compliance

Indicators	Mean	SD	Interpretation
As a pupil, I...			
1. do well in school as requested by my parents/ guardian.	4.16	0.78	Practiced
2. am kind to everyone in the school because my family urged me to do so.	4.10	0.92	Practiced
3. complete my class works as encouraged by my parents/ guardian.	4.44	0.75	Practiced
4. stay in the seat and avoid talking with my classmates as advised by my family members.	3.69	0.93	Practiced
5. ask permission to the teacher when going out as reminded by the elders.	4.63	0.61	Highly Practiced
Overall	4.20	0.52	Practiced

Legend: 4.50-5.0-Strongly Agree/ Highly Practiced

3.50-4.49-Agree/ Practiced

2.50-3.49- Moderately Agree/ Moderately Practiced

1.50-2.49-Disagree/ Slightly Practiced

1.00-1.49-Strongly Disagree/ Not Practiced

Presented in Table 9 was the perception of the respondents on social influence as to compliance. Indicator 5, "As a pupil, I ask permission to the teacher when going out as reminded by the elders" is noted to have the highest mean of 4.63. This shows that pupils "highly practiced" following the tradition or cultural norm of seeking permission from their teacher before leaving the classroom or school premises. They do so because they may have been advised or reminded by their elders, such as parents or older family members, as a sign of respect and discipline. This indicates that this behavior is not only expected but also reinforced by their family and community. The social elements such as family values and beliefs influence pupils' compliance with societal norms and rules. The perceived importance of their family's viewpoint, their relationship with their family members, and their level of independence and autonomy may all influence the students' compliance with their family's advice in these instances.

Moreover, indicator 4, "As a pupil, I stay in the seat and avoid talking with my classmates as advised by my family members" got the lowest mean of 3.69 but is also interpreted as practiced by the pupil-respondents. Most pupils nowadays are constantly reminded by their parents, guardian or family members to refrain loitering and being noisy for them to focus their attention in the class and minimize distractions in the classroom. This shows that the students' adherence to this family advice displays that their values, beliefs, or expectations have probably influenced them.

Furthermore, an overall mean of 4.20 with a standard deviation of 0.52 is presented in table 10 with interpretation of "Agree" which displays that the social influence in terms of compliance of the pupils is "practiced". There is a great level of compliance among pupils in which they act and do things in accordance with the request/s of other people. Pupils may accomplish the assigned works, perform well in school, exhibit good conduct toward teachers and classmates, as reminded and requested by their parents, guardian, family members, elders and other people who have influence over them. Pupils who are encouraged to obey their parents or elders tend to have a higher regard for authority people, including their teachers. They are more likely to obey instructions, follow regulations, and can contribute to order and discipline in the classroom.

Moreover, Huang and Lamb (2014) explained that compliance development is an indication of self-control, socializing, and even moral improvement in children. As children get older, internal factors become more important as mediators of compliance, which is first imposed and sustained by external demands such as requests of parents/guardian, family members and/or elders.

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Table 10. Mean Perception of the Respondents to the Classroom Social Dynamics as to Social Influence in terms of Obedience

Indicators	Mean	SD	Interpretation
As a pupil, I...			
1. avoid negative or bad behavior during class as ordered by my parents/ guardian.	4.28	0.85	Practiced
2. do not hurt my classmates or other pupils to avoid getting hurt or punished by my parents/ guardian.	4.11	0.90	Practiced
3. stay out of trouble in school as commanded by the elders.	4.29	0.91	Practiced
4. cooperate in the group activities as demanded by the group leader.	4.53	0.70	Highly Practiced
5. help in cleaning the classroom as commanded by the class president and/or class officers.	4.52	0.64	Highly Practiced
6. do not bully others as directed by the school guidance counselor and principal.	4.20	0.76	Practiced
Overall	4.32	0.53	Practiced

Legend: 4.50-5.0-Strongly Agree/ Highly Practiced

3.50-4.49-Agree/ Practiced

2.50-3.49- Moderately Agree/ Moderately Practiced

1.50-2.49-Disagree/ Slightly Practiced

1.00-1.49-Strongly Disagree/ Not Practiced

Table 10 displays indicator 4 as having the highest mean of 4.53 which tells that pupils cooperate in the group activities as demanded by their group leader. Pupil-respondents “highly practiced” obedience in this indicator, which suggests that they behave in the group as commanded by their group leader in position of authority other than their teacher. One of the rules that teachers set before doing group activities is to cooperate with the group members. Teachers also assign group leaders who will lead the group in accomplishing their tasks. When members of a group obey with the orders of a leader, even if those orders conflict with their personal beliefs or principles, they are demonstrating their willingness to follow the norms of the group. In order to promote obedience among group members, group leaders may also employ other strategies of social influence, such as persuasion or coercion.

Meanwhile, indicator 2 with the lowest mean of 4.11 states that pupils do not hurt their classmates or other pupils to avoid getting hurt or punished by their parents/ guardian. This implies that pupil-respondents “practiced” obedience in this indicator. This means that students are aware that hurting others is wrong and may result in their receiving harsh punishment from their parents or guardians. They are aware that if they hurt one of their classmates, their guardians might discipline or reprimand them. They consequently decide not to harm others in particular circumstances in order to obey their parents/ guardian and to avoid potential consequences.

It can also be gathered in Table 10 the overall mean of 4.32 and standard deviation of 0.53 which shows that the respondents perceived the classroom social dynamics as to social influence is “practiced” in terms of obedience. It means that pupils interact in the classroom by obeying and behaving because someone in a position of authority, other than their teacher, has told them to. Students may feel obligated or respectful to obey authority figures' requests or directions when they come into contact with them, especially in school settings. This deference to authority may result from a number of things, such as socialization, cultural norms, perceived knowledge, fear of consequences, and a desire to please or stay out of trouble. Pupils tend to stay out of trouble, avoid bad behavior, cooperate and do assigned tasks, and follow instructions as ordered by their parents/ guardian, elders, group leaders, class president and/or officers, principal and/or school authorities.

As stated by Hellmer et al. (2021), obedience is acting in accordance with the demands of an authoritative figure. It occurs as a result of particular directives from authorities and surrender to the majority's demand. Unlike pursuing positive internal rewards, obedience is initiated by an authoritative person and motivated by a desire to avoid undesirable external consequences.

Table 11. Summary of Mean Perception of the Respondents to the Classroom Social Dynamics as to Social Influence

Social Influence	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Conformity	4.39	0.46	Practiced
Expectation	4.50	0.45	Highly Practiced
Compliance	4.20	0.52	Practiced
Obedience	4.32	0.53	Practiced
Overall	4.35	0.49	Practiced

Legend: 4.50-5.0-Strongly Agree/ Highly Practiced

3.50-4.49-Agree/ Practiced

2.50-3.49- Moderately Agree/ Moderately Practiced

1.50-2.49-Disagree/ Slightly Practiced

1.00-1.49-Strongly Disagree/ Not Practiced

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It is summarized in Table 11 the weighted mean distribution on the responses on the classroom social dynamics as to social influence. It can be gleaned that expectation got the highest mean of 4.50. It demonstrates that, among the social influence forms, expectation is the most strongly agreed upon by pupil-respondents, implying that this social influence is “highly practiced”. Pupils behave or act as influenced and expected by other people. They may follow instructions, complete assignments, participate in activities, strive to meet academic standards, excel in assignments or tests, or demonstrate their knowledge or skills, to meet the social expectations and social acceptance. The presence of expectations in the classroom social dynamics indicates that students perceive certain norms, regulations, or guidelines established by the teacher or the social group. Learners are typically motivated to meet these expectations by a fear of social disapproval. These expectations came from their social roles as a student and a member of the school, as an intermediate or grade six pupil, or as a male or female.

A look at the table shows the other forms of social influence such as conformity which got a mean of 4.39, obedience with a mean of 4.32, and compliance with the lowest mean of 4.20. This imply that these three other forms of social influence are “practiced” by the pupils in classroom social dynamics. Pupils conform and obey to their teachers, parents, elders, and/or peer due to the societal standards and norms. Compliance, having the lowest mean, but still agreed by the pupil-respondents, may imply that it is “practiced” by pupils. Learners comply by following guidelines regarding behavior, interactions, and academic requirements due to the direct or indirect request of other people such as their parents/ guardian, family members, elders, or other people.

An overall mean of 4.35 and standard deviation of 0.49 with a verbal interpretation of “agree” is shown. It shows that the classroom social dynamics as to social influence are “practiced” by the pupil-respondents. It implies that the students are actively engaging in behaviors that are influenced by their peers or the social environment. They do things in the classroom which are affected by the thoughts, feelings, and behaviors of others such as their classmates, peer, parents/ guardian, family members, elders, school authorities, and others. This could include adopting the opinions or beliefs of influential peers, conforming to group norms, imitating behaviors of popular individuals, or seeking approval and acceptance from other people. Pupils may follow rules and instructions, participate in various activities, behave properly or adhere to academic policies by the influence of others. Raising hands before speaking, keeping the classroom tidy, completing assignments, participating in class activities, or submitting work on time, entering the classroom quietly, taking their seats, lining up for activities, attending classes regularly, following the schedule, or even refraining from disruptive behavior are all things that students can do if they perceive that either other people are doing the same, or expecting them to do, or requesting and ordering them. All of this is brought about by social standards, roles, and norms. Social influence plays a role in shaping the dynamics within a classroom setting. Other people can impact students' enthusiasm to learn and participate in classroom activities.

As supported by Runco (2014), interpersonal and environmental factors both have a social influence. Both of these factors contribute to social influence by affecting individuals' attitudes, beliefs, and behaviors. By addressing these factors, teachers can positively shape classroom social dynamics, foster student well-being, and improve academic outcomes.

Table 12. Perceived Extent of Supportive Learning Environment Manifested as to Respondents' Academic Performance

Indicators	Mean	SD	Interpretation
As a pupil, I...			
1. participate in the class discussion and pass and accomplish daily exercises or tasks.	4.58	0.62	Highly Manifested
2. contribute to class discussion by answering questions of the teacher and explaining my ideas to the class.	4.30	0.66	Manifested
3. do well and pass the written work or assessment given in each lesson.	4.42	0.70	Manifested
4. perform well on the activities assigned in each lesson.	4.43	0.65	Manifested
5. have complete and correct assignment.	4.37	0.86	Manifested
6. show mastery of the lesson by passing the quizzes in every week.	4.30	0.75	Manifested
7. get pass grades in the periodical tests.	4.18	0.82	Manifested
Overall	4.37	0.48	Manifested

Legend: 4.50-5.0-Strongly Agree/ Highly Manifested

3.50-4.49-Agree/ Manifested

2.50-3.49- Moderately Agree/ Moderately Manifested

1.50-2.49-Disagree/ Slightly Manifested

1.00-1.49-Strongly Disagree/ Not Manifested

Presented in Table 12 is the perceived extent of supportive learning environment manifested as to respondents' academic performance. Indicator 1 has the highest mean of 4.58 which shows that the pupil-respondents strongly agree that they participate in the class discussion and pass and accomplish daily exercises or tasks. This may imply that the supportive learning environment is “highly manifested” as pupils perceive themselves as participating in the discussion and accomplishing tasks. It means that they are involved in the learning process which could be by raising hands, responding to questions, giving queries, sharing and expressing

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ideas, doing exercises and tasks related to the lesson, and the like. In this manner, it may indicate a positive indication of pupils' academic performance and progress in their studies, which can be more likely to happen when there is a supportive learning environment created by student-student and teacher-student positive interaction or relationship. The aforementioned activities are all categorized as performance tasks and one of the components in the DepEd Grading System as stipulated in DepEd Order No.8, s.2015 or the Policy Guidelines on Classroom Assessment for the K to 12 Basic Education Program. Performance-Based Tasks have the largest weight distribution in determining the grades of pupils per learning areas.

Meanwhile, indicator 7 which states that pupil-respondents get pass grades in the periodical tests, is noted to have the lowest mean of 4.18 but still agreed upon by the respondents. Periodical Tests or Quarterly Assessments are being done four times in a school year and have 20% weight distribution in determining the grades per learning area as per the DepEd Grading System. Though it has the smallest percentage, it is important to pass by the students for it reflects and measures student learning on the competencies taught in every quarter. Students tend to understand the material better and are more likely to receive passing results on these examinations when they feel at ease and motivated in the teaching-learning process, which is an indication of a supportive learning environment manifested as to pupils' good academic performance.

Furthermore, an overall mean of 4.37 and standard deviation of 0.48 is displayed on table 13 which shows that the pupil-respondents' academic performance "manifested" a supportive learning environment. It implies that if there is a presence of a healthy learning atmosphere in the class, it creates the conditions necessary for students to thrive academically. When a student perceive that his/her teacher is actively listening to pupils, encourage respectful dialogue and expression of ideas, non-judgmental, encouraging everyone in the class to respect and support one another, and other pupils in the class do the same, that certain student is more likely to have courage and be motivated to perform well in the class.

As supported by Lamas (2015) that the external, internal, and environmental factors that characterize abilities and experiences have an impact on one's performance. Intellectual ability, personality, desire, aptitude, interests, study habits, self-worth, and the teacher-student relationship are just a few of the factors that influence academic performance. Thus, pupils' good performance is one of the manifestations of a supportive learning environment.

Table 13. Perceived Extent of Supportive Learning Environment Manifested as to Respondents' Engagement

Indicators	Mean	SD	Interpretation
As a pupil, I...			
1. listen attentively in class discussion.	4.45	0.62	Manifested
2. understand and follow the instructions of my teacher during class.	4.62	0.56	Highly Manifested
3. express my ideas or opinions in the class.	4.31	0.68	Manifested
4. enjoy working and learning with my classmates in different activities.	4.57	0.64	Highly Manifested
5. take notes in class to ensure that I remember the information discussed.	4.43	0.61	Manifested
6. spend time and effort in doing outputs or projects.	4.58	0.58	Highly Manifested
7. enjoy the lessons and tasks in the class.	4.45	0.69	Manifested
Overall	4.49	0.42	Manifested

Legend: 4.50-5.0-Strongly Agree/ Highly Manifested

3.50-4.49-Agree/ Manifested

2.50-3.49- Moderately Agree/ Moderately Manifested

1.50-2.49-Disagree/ Slightly Manifested

1.00-1.49-Strongly Disagree/ Not Manifested

Table 13 reveals the highest mean of 4.62 which shows that the pupil-respondents strongly agree in indicator 2 which states that they understand and follow the instructions of their teacher during class. This shows that supportive learning environment is "highly manifested" as pupils tend to pay close attention to the teacher's instructions during class. They are focused on the teacher's words and are actively listening to what is being communicated. The pupils' assertion implies that they are actively engaged in the learning process. They are actively participating and putting effort into understanding and following the instructions given by the teacher. This may be possible when teachers actively listen to students and address any questions or concerns they may have. Teachers could also provide personalized explanation of the instruction to some pupils who needed it most. Encouraging students to ask questions and actively engaging in discussions foster a supportive learning environment. With this, students feel more comfortable asking questions, seeking clarification, and attentively listening in class discussions, which may lead to better understanding and following of instructions, thus reflects an increased engagement.

Meanwhile, Table 13 also displays the lowest mean of 4.31 which shows that pupil-respondents "agree" in indicator 3 which states that they express their ideas or opinions in the class. It suggests that the pupils are actively involved in the learning process and are willing to participate by sharing their thoughts, ideas, and perspectives. This indicates a level of engagement with the subject matter and a desire to contribute to the classroom discussions. This may be possible if the classroom or learning environment is free from criticism or judgment from their classmates or the teacher. The dynamics between the teacher and the

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students which can be seen in an instance when teachers and pupils in the class respectfully accept and recognize pupils' ideas and suggestions, can influence pupils' confidence to voice out their thoughts or opinions.

Similarly, this table shows an overall mean of 4.49 and a standard deviation of 0.42 which shows that the respondents' engagement "manifested" a supportive learning environment. Students feel included, accepted, and safe in a favorable environment for learning. They are more likely to engage in and contribute to classroom discussions when they feel at ease and appreciated, regardless of their background, talents, or identities. They tend to put effort and time in attentively listening and involving in the teaching-learning process, doing class works, sharing their insights, and other similar activities, when the classroom promotes diversity, equity, inclusion and a sense of belonging.

According to Shernoff, et al. (2016), student engagement fluctuates from one instructional episode to the next due to differences in environmental complexity. Creating learning environments that inspire focus, enjoyment, curiosity, self-esteem, and intrinsic motivation is an excellent goal. Creating supportive and challenging learning environments may be one of the most effective strategies for teachers to enhance pupil engagement in learning. Therefore, pupils' high engagement in the class manifests a supportive learning environment.

Table 14. Perceived Extent of Supportive Learning Environment Manifested as to Respondents' Self-Regulation

Indicators	Mean	SD	Interpretation
As a pupil, I...			
1. can keep my attention focused on the class discussion or activities.	4.33	0.72	Manifested
2. am able to control my thoughts and emotions at school.	4.42	0.62	Manifested
3. manage to follow the rules whether or not the teacher is present.	4.28	0.77	Manifested
4. find ways to keep myself motivated in doing the assigned classwork.	4.42	0.62	Manifested
5. set goals for myself that I want to achieve in the class.	4.47	0.65	Manifested
6. believe in my own abilities in learning.	4.61	0.57	Highly Manifested
7. am determined to do and learn better	4.56	0.61	Highly Manifested
8. manage my time in order to pass outputs or finish class works on time.	4.39	0.67	Manifested
Overall	4.43	0.45	Manifested

Legend: 4.50-5.0-Strongly Agree/ Highly Manifested

3.50-4.49-Agree/ Manifested

2.50-3.49- Moderately Agree/ Moderately Manifested

1.50-2.49-Disagree/ Slightly Manifested

1.00-1.49-Strongly Disagree/ Not Manifested

As can be gleaned at table 14, pupils "strongly agree" in indicator 6 which states that they believe in their own abilities in learning and is noted to have the highest mean of 4.61. This shows that supportive learning environment is "highly manifested" in terms of self-regulation. When teachers create a healthy atmosphere by being approachable and available to students, fostering a sense of trust and open communication, encouraging peer collaboration and support, and allowing students to learn from and help one another, pupils are more likely to develop self-control, a positive self-perception, and a sense of self-efficacy. Students may have self-belief in their abilities by having the conviction that through effort and efficient learning techniques, as well as with the help of others, they can comprehend new ideas, overcome obstacles, and enhance their performance. As pupils develop their self-belief, they tend to manage themselves skillfully and be confident enough to interact with the people in their classroom academically and behaviorally.

On the other hand, indicator 3 got the lowest mean of 4.28, which states that they manage to follow the rules whether or not the teacher is present. This claim of the respondents that they can follow the rules even in the absence of the teacher suggests a level of self-regulation. It involves managing oneself without external prompts or supervision. It implies that these students have some degree of self-control and are able to follow the rules on their own. Whether the teacher is around or not, pupils may adhere in the classroom rules such as keeping silent, behaving accordingly, keeping the classroom clean and organized, avoiding trouble, and the like. This self-regulation in such instances can be encouraged by a supportive learning environment in which they also feel respected and appreciated by the teacher and peers or classmates, which may lead to them doing the same in the classroom.

On the whole, an average mean of 4.43 with standard deviation of 0.45 described as agree is obtained in terms of the given parameters in Table 14. It shows that supportive learning environment is "manifested" as to pupils' self-regulation. This implies that when students feel supported in their learning environment, they are more likely to engage in self-regulated learning behaviors. When students feel connected and supported by their teachers and peers, they are more likely to feel safe, motivated, and engaged. They are more likely to manage their emotions, time and thoughts effectively, can keep the attention in the class and motivation in class works, and develop self-efficacy and self-determination.

This is supported by the study of Amaro (2023) that when children are unable to manage their thoughts, feelings, and conduct, it can be difficult for them to form and keep friendships, relate to others, organize their schoolwork, and express their emotions in suitable ways. Strong student achievement is dependent on teaching children how to express their emotions

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appropriately, consider the consequences of their actions, and make meaningful connections. A supportive school environment can help to develop these qualities.

Table 15. Perceived Extent of Supportive Learning Environment Manifested as to Respondents' Self-Resiliency

Indicators	Mean	SD	Interpretation
As a pupil, I...			
1. think of myself as a strong person.	3.98	1.00	Manifested
2. use negative comment or feedback in my work as a motivation to do better.	4.24	0.78	Manifested
3. am hopeful and positive that I can pass my poor quizzes or test results next time.	4.55	0.67	Highly Manifested
4. can find solution when I encounter difficult assigned tasks.	4.41	0.59	Manifested
5. try to answer in discussion or recitation even if my answer is incorrect or unsure.	4.27	0.88	Manifested
6. know when and whom to ask for help in difficult time.	4.41	0.66	Manifested
7. will positively come and participate in class everyday even if I am experiencing problems at home.	4.42	0.71	Manifested
Overall	4.33	0.46	Manifested

Legend: 4.50-5.0-Strongly Agree/ Highly Manifested

3.50-4.49-Agree/ Manifested

2.50-3.49- Moderately Agree/ Moderately Manifested

1.50-2.49-Disagree/ Slightly Manifested

1.00-1.49-Strongly Disagree/ Not Manifested

Table 15 shows the perceived extent of supportive learning environment manifested as to respondents' self-resiliency. Indicator 3 which states that "As a pupil, I am hopeful and positive that I can pass my poor quizzes or test results next time" got the highest mean of 4.55. This shows that supportive learning environment is "highly manifested" in terms of pupils' self-resiliency. This implies that despite initial setback of receiving low scores on their quizzes or tests, they remain optimistic and believe they can improve their performance in the future. The pupil's statement reflects a positive mindset, indicating that they are determined and motivated to work harder and achieve better results. Pupils nowadays should possess these self-resiliency qualities and it can be fostered with the help of a healthy learning environment. Teachers and classmates or peers may provide emotional support to help pupils to be resilient. With this support system, pupils may recognize their current performance as unsatisfactory but choose to see it as an opportunity for growth rather than a reason to give up. Resilient students understand that failure is a part of the learning process. If they receive a poor grade on an assignment or test, they won't let it discourage them. Instead, they will reflect on their mistakes, learn from them, and work harder to improve their performance in the future.

On the other hand, indicator 1 which states that "As a pupil, I think of myself as a strong person" got the lowest mean of 3.98. This implies that pupil-respondents agree and believe that they are strong. It shows that supportive learning environment is "manifested" in terms of self-resiliency. This implies that they perceive themselves as resilient, emotionally and mentally capable, and able to handle difficult situations effectively. It suggests that they have confidence in their abilities to face challenges, overcome obstacles, and endure hardships. In a supportive learning environment, teachers and peers ensure that students feel safe, both physically and emotionally. They are encouraged to express their thoughts, opinions, and concerns without fear of judgment or ridicule. They provide consistent encouragement and positive reinforcement for students' efforts and achievements. Teachers, counselors, and other school staff are available to provide guidance, assistance, and emotional support when needed. These resources help students develop sense of belonging, confidence and strategies to cope with difficulties, boosting their self-resiliency. When faced with a difficult subject or concept, a resilient strong pupil will persevere through their struggles. They may seek additional help from teachers or peers, utilize available resources such as textbooks or online materials, and maintain a positive attitude to keep trying until they understand the topic. Pupils are also often face an increased workload and multiple assignments. Resilient strong students will develop effective time management skills, prioritize tasks, and organize their schedule to ensure they meet deadlines and complete their work to the best of their ability.

A look at the table shows that the overall mean score of the pupil-respondents relative to the statements on self-resiliency is 4.33 with standard deviation of 0.46 and interpreted as agree. It implies that the pupils perceived themselves as resilient and it "manifested" a supportive learning environment. Self-resilient pupils tend to possess a sense of belief in their capacity to overcome challenges, ability to bounce back from setbacks, maintain a positive attitude, and keep striving for success. They are optimistic and have a sense of own strength, have positive mindset which focuses on their strengths and progress rather than getting discouraged by setbacks, can find solution and know when and whom to seek for help in difficult times. These can be fostered by a favorable classroom culture where students feel empowered, supported, and motivated to succeed.

Similarly, Whatman (2020) states that resilience changes with time; depending on a person's abilities, circumstances, resources, and environment, they may be resilient one day but not the next. The levels of the individual, family, community, or culture have all been widely categorized as protective factors that act to build or strengthen resilience. Whole families or communities must frequently cooperate and receive help if they want to become more resilient. Thus, pupils' self-resiliency can be manifested by a supportive learning environment.

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Table 16. Summary of Perceived Extent of Supportive Learning Environment

Supportive Learning Environment	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Academic Performance	4.37	0.48	Manifested
Engagement	4.49	0.42	Manifested
Self-Regulation	4.43	0.45	Manifested
Self-Resiliency	4.33	0.46	Manifested
Overall	4.41	0.45	Manifested

Legend: 4.50-5.0-Strongly Agree/ Highly Manifested

3.50-4.49-Agree/ Manifested

2.50-3.49- Moderately Agree/ Moderately Manifested

1.50-2.49-Disagree/ Slightly Manifested

1.00-1.49-Strongly Disagree/ Not Manifested

It is presented in Table 16 the summary of the weighted mean distribution on the responses on the supportive learning environment. The respondents “agree” to all of the indicators such as academic performance (4.37), engagement (4.49), self-regulation (4.43), and self-resiliency (4.33). This shows that pupil-respondents perceived that supportive learning environment is “manifested”. When teachers and peers in classroom social dynamics create a supportive environment to pupils where they encourage freedom of self-expression and collaboration, listen, trust, support and respect one another, pupils are more likely to perform, participate and involve in the teaching-learning process as well as develop their self-management, efficacy and positive outlook and mindset.

It can also be gleaned from the table that respondents’ perception on their engagement got the highest mean of 4.49. It shows that the respondents perceived that supportive learning environment is “manifested” in terms of pupils’ engagement. It suggests that the high level of student involvement was influenced by a helpful learning environment. A supportive learning environment may play a crucial role in pupils’ engagement in the classroom. Students tend to be more inclined to actively participate, take chances, and invest themselves to their learning in a favorable environment where they feel respected and encouraged.

Meanwhile, self-resiliency is noted to have the lowest mean of 4.33, but also got “agree” rating based on the perception of the respondents. It shows that the respondents perceived that supportive learning environment is “manifested” in terms of pupils’ self-resiliency. It indicates that an environment where pupils feel and perceive that they are valued and supported by teachers and their peers may tend to influence and contribute to their sense of belonging which fosters self-resiliency. The emphasis in a supportive learning environment is on effort, tenacity, and the conviction that intelligence and ability can be developed. By instilling in students the idea that they can overcome challenges and advance their skills via perseverance and hard work, this growth mindset culture fosters resilience.

On the whole, the overall mean is 4.41 and the overall standard deviation is 0.49. As the pupil-respondents “agree” on all of the indicators, this shows that supportive learning environment is “manifested”. This implies that there is a manifestation of supportive environment to learners as they perceived themselves that they perform well and engage in the class and has self-regulation and self-resiliency. A supportive learning environment that is manifested in these areas indicates that students are thriving academically, emotionally, and socially. They are actively engaged in their learning, have the ability to regulate their own learning and behavior, and are resilient in the face of challenges, which may lead to favorable outcomes in their learning journey. For children’ cognitive, emotional, and social growth, a conducive learning environment in the classroom is essential. It fosters a welcoming, safe environment where all students may participate fully in their education and feel appreciated and respected. Constructive teacher-student relationships, clear expectations and guidelines, a student-centered approach, inclusive practices, encouraging peer interaction and collaboration, effective classroom management, celebrating effort and success, a safe and comfortable physical environment, a supportive classroom culture, and differentiated instruction are all factors that may contribute to this healthy environment.

According to Monteiro, et.al. (2021), students will be motivated to interact with their teachers and peers, engage in a variety of activities and learning spaces, and strengthen their sense of school identity in a supportive environment.

Table 17. Correlation between Supportive Learning Environment and Classroom Social Dynamics as to Teachers’ Influence

Classroom Social Dynamics	Supportive Learning Environment			
	Academic Performance	Engagement	Self- Regulation	Self-Resiliency
Legitimate	.153	.248**	.188*	.158
Teachers’ Referent	.336**	.403**	.266**	.335**
Influence Expert	.275**	.399**	.284**	.253**
Reward	.236*	.280**	.255**	.340**
Coercive	-.097	-.034	-.149	.065

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

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Table 17 displays the correlation between supportive learning environment and classroom social dynamics as to teachers' influence. It shows that legitimate as teachers' influence has no significant relationship with pupils' academic performance. It may imply that the teachers' observed ability to set standards in the classroom have no direct bearing on pupils' ability to perform in the class. It suggests that variables other than the teacher's observed legitimacy or authority tend to be responsible for the students' academic performance. Legitimate influence or the teacher's ability to establish guidelines and maintain their authority in the classroom is typically considered an important aspect of effective teaching. This finding, however, raises the possibility that other factors, such as students' individual abilities, their desire to learn, home environment, their parental support, or even external factors like socioeconomic status or peer influence, may have a greater impact on students' academic performance than the perceived legitimacy of their teachers. On the other hand, findings showed that legitimate influence has significant relationship to pupils' engagement. It may indicate that when teachers are perceived as legitimate figures of authority, it has an impact on students' level of engagement. Students may be more likely to actively participate in class, pay attention to instruction, and feel motivated to learn when they observed their teachers as credible and authoritative. The perception of legitimacy can be influenced by various factors, including the teacher's authority in setting expectations and standards as well as clarity of communication in establishing rules and guidelines for behavior in the classroom. When teachers create this environment, it may help to enhance students' engagement and foster a more effective learning experience. Likewise, legitimate influence of teachers was also found to be significant in pupils' self-regulation. This implies that students may be more likely to exhibit self-control, focus on tasks, set goals, and regulate their behavior in alignment with classroom expectations when they observe their teachers as credible and authoritative. The perception of legitimacy can be influenced by factors such as the teacher's consistency in enforcing rules, the establishment of clear expectations and the provision of guidance and support. When teachers create a structured learning environment, it may contribute to students' ability to manage their behavior, emotions, and cognitive processes. Moreover, findings showed that teachers' legitimate influence is not significant to pupils' self-resiliency. It implies that other factors beyond the teacher's perceived authority are more likely to be more influential in shaping students' resilience. Some of these elements might include a student's unique traits, familial support, peer interactions, personal experiences, or other outside elements that help them navigate and get beyond challenges. Though teachers' legitimate influence is crucial for creating an environment where students feel empowered, this result implies that teachers' influence on students' self-resiliency may be indirect or mediated by other factors.

In terms of referent influence of teachers, it is presented in table 17 that it has significant relationship with pupils' academic performance. This may imply that when teachers are observed by the pupils to be caring, sincere, approachable and a model that they want to emulate, it may contribute on how well the students perform academically. When teachers have these qualities as perceived by the pupils, it may help them to be motivated to study hard and accomplish tasks in the classroom. Similarly, teachers' referent influence was also found to be significant on pupils' engagement. It implies that teachers' ability to influence pupils by their attractive personality may have an impact on how engaged students are in their learning process. It also implies that the observed referent influence of teachers has a significant influence in creating an atmosphere that encourages meaningful and active student participation. Higher levels of attention, interest, and involvement that students show in the class are more likely to be fostered by teachers who are regarded as likeable and approachable, fair, encourage student collaboration and participation, and develop supportive relationships with their students. Referent teachers' influence is also significant to pupils' self-regulation. It suggests that teachers who exhibit attributes that students find appealing may have an impact on how they monitor, regulate, and adjust their thoughts, feelings, and behaviors in order to accomplish particular goals. As to pupils' resiliency, it was also found out to have significant relationship to teachers' referent influence. This implies that teachers can play a significant role in helping students develop and strengthen their ability to adapt, cope, and recover from difficult situations, stress, or adversity. Referent teachers who foster a growth mindset, encourage a positive and optimistic outlook, provide opportunities for students to face and overcome challenges, and offer support and guidance in times of difficulty can influence students' self-resiliency. By modeling and promoting resilience, teachers can empower students to develop coping strategies, maintain a sense of determination and perseverance, and bounce back from setbacks. Pupils may have the tendency to be more optimistic in different challenges and even failures that they may encounter, since they feel secured that they have their teacher to rely on.

Teachers' influence in terms of expert is also significantly related to pupils' academic performance. This may suggest that teachers who are knowledgeable in their subject area, have effective teaching methods, and are pedagogically skilled are more likely to have an impact on their students' academic performance. Teachers who possess expertise are able to create and deliver interesting and challenging lessons. They can offer relevant and current knowledge, encourage critical thinking abilities, curiosity, and enthusiasm, and establish a nurturing educational atmosphere, all of which may help students perform better academically. Likewise, teachers' expert influence is found to be significant to pupils' engagement which may imply that the observed competence and expertise of teachers may affect pupils' higher level of involvement and participation in the class. As observed by the learners, teachers who are knowledgeable about their subjects and instructional strategies are more likely to design engaging learning opportunities for their pupils. They have an in-depth understanding of the material and know how to communicate it to capture students' attention. Their knowledge enables them to develop and put into practice dynamic instructional tactics that encourage student engagement and active learning. Additionally, this expert influence was found to have significant relationship to pupils'

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self-regulation. It implies that skilled teachers can support the growth of pupils' capacity for self-regulation. Teachers enable their students to take ownership of their own learning, control their behavior, and acquire the skills necessary for independent and lifelong learning through modeling, clear instruction, feedback, goal-setting, autonomy, and a nurturing learning atmosphere. As to self-resiliency, it is also significant to teachers' expert influence. This indicates that teachers may impact the pupils' mindset and optimism. Students may receive coping mechanisms from knowledgeable teachers to deal with pressure, disappointments, and difficulties. They show pupils how to solve problems, communicate to themselves positively, and foster self-efficacy. Teachers may increase students' resilience by developing a feeling of confidence and belief in their own talents as well as empowering them to overcome obstacles and increase their resilience through nurturing self-efficacy and providing students with appropriate coping skills.

It can also be gleaned from table 17 that reward influence of teachers has significant influence in pupils' academic performance which may imply that the observed ability of the teachers to provide rewards, incentives, or recognition may have an impact on how well pupils perform academically. These may serve as motivators for students to put in more effort in their studies to pass or excel in written and oral assessment, performance tasks, and completion of class works. When students know that they will be rewarded and/or recognized for their achievements or progress, it can increase their motivation to excel academically. This reward influence of teachers is also found to be significant in pupils' engagement which may indicate that the observed ability of the teachers to provide rewards may play a role in promoting and sustaining students' active participation and involvement in the learning process. Rewards can capture students' attention and spark their interest in the subject matter. When students know that they can earn rewards for their engagement and participation, they are more likely to pay attention, participate actively in class discussions, and show interest in the topics being taught. Additionally, this influence is significant to pupils' self-regulation. This implies that it may contribute in fostering students' ability to regulate their own learning and behavior. When students know that they can earn rewards for meeting certain targets or milestones, it may encourage them to set their own learning goals and take responsibility for their progress. In terms of pupils' self-resiliency, teachers' reward influence has significant relationship to it as well. This may show that when pupils observed that their teachers appreciate their effort by giving rewards, recognition and/or reinforcements, it may help them to be resilient. When students are rewarded for their efforts, they internalize the belief that they have the skills and resources to overcome difficulties, leading to increased self-confidence and resilience.

Furthermore, table 17 shows that there is no significant relationship between coercive influence of teachers and pupils' academic performance. This may imply that the observed teachers' ability to give punishment or undesirable consequences for pupils' non-compliance does not directly impact or predict the academic achievements or performance of students. Coercive influence typically relies on assertiveness and exercise of authority, control, or punishments. However, academic performance is often associated with factors like student motivation, commitment, and autonomy, thus, coercion may have no bearing on pupils' performance academically. Likewise, coercive influence also was found to be not significant to pupils' engagement which may imply that teachers' ability to influence students with the use of undesirable consequences does not directly affect the pupils' level of involvement in the class. Student engagement can be influenced by the overall classroom climate and opportunities for active participation. When teachers prioritize providing meaningful learning experiences, students are more likely to be engaged, regardless of coercive influences. In addition, teachers' coercive influence of teachers was found to be not significantly related to pupils' self-regulation and self-resiliency. This implies that the observed teachers' assertiveness and use of undesirable consequences have no impact on pupils' ability to self-regulate and be resilient. While teachers' coercion may have an influence on external factors such as classroom rules, consequences or for disciplinary reasons, the development of self-regulation and self-resiliency skills is also influenced by internal factors such as individual temperament, motivation, mindset, personal experiences, and support networks. It's possible that these internal factors have a more significant impact on self-regulation than coercive influence. Thus, either pupils observed their teachers to have coercive influence or not, this has nothing to do and no bearing on their self-management and outlook.

On the whole, the findings show that teachers' influence in terms of referent, expert, and reward is significantly related to all the variables of supportive learning environment including pupils' performance, engagement, self-regulation and self-resiliency; whereas teachers' legitimate influence is significantly related to pupils' engagement and self-regulation. The results may imply that the teachers' influences which are observed by the learners have an impact on the development of pupils' academic and socio-emotional development. Teachers play a crucial role in shaping social dynamics within the classroom, thus, teachers' influences and pleasant interactions, relationships and behavior toward pupils may contribute in developing an environment that fosters learning, growth, constructive student experiences and over-all development. With the teachers' actions, attitudes and instructional practices, the dynamics and climate in the classroom can be affected. As pupils observed these behavior and influences of teachers, they may respond and even adapt these behaviors in terms of participating in the class and interacting with their teachers and classmates. On the other hand, teachers' practice of influences such as by being too authoritative by its position and coercion have no relationship on the supportive learning environment. This implies that given other external factors that may have a greater impact on these outcomes for students, whether the teacher is assertive or not when teaching, dealing with, or disciplining the students, this has no direct impact and does not affect the students' academic performance, engagement, self-regulation, and self-resiliency. It is

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vital for teachers to be sensible of their influences and strive to foster an encouraging and healthy learning environment by building strong teacher-student connections, managing the classroom well, providing emotional support, and providing feedback and advice to students.

The findings of this study were supported by Vlckova, et.al (2015) which highlights that student motivation and cognitive and affective learning were positively correlated with referent, expert, and reward power (viewed as prosocial forms of power), whereas legitimate and coercive power (viewed as antisocial forms of power) was adversely correlated with these learning outcomes. Positive associations with prosocial types of power and negative associations with antisocial kinds of power were found between students' views of teacher confirmation behaviors. Likewise, the study findings were also similar to Aldridge & Rowntree (2022), wherein they also found out that because teachers set good models for social behavior, learning attitudes, and concept acceptance, their interactions with students have an impact on the educational environment. There is a strong relationship between learning goal orientation and teacher support. This is significant for teachers in terms of their role in creating the learning environment, including the instructional strategies and support systems they provide. Self-efficacy was also influenced by teacher support, and students are more likely to be motivated to accomplish prescribed tasks if they believe their teacher cares about them.

Table 18. Correlation between Supportive Learning Environment and Classroom Social Dynamics as to Social Influence

Classroom Social Dynamics		Supportive Learning Environment			
		Academic Performance	Engagement	Self-Regulation	Self-Resiliency
Social Influence	Conformity	.348**	.479**	.248**	.331**
	Expectation	.499**	.588**	.437**	.323**
	Compliance	.612**	.535**	.500**	.375**
	Obedience	.639**	.541**	.555**	.273**

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Presented in Table 18 is the correlation between supportive learning environment and classroom social dynamics as to social influence. As can be gleaned in the table, conformity as social influence, has a significant relationship to pupils' academic performance. It may imply that when pupils conform or adjust their thoughts, attitudes, and behaviors in order to align with the positive social standards and norms, it has an impact on their performance at school, thus, there is a possibility for pupils to be more motivated to perform well academically. Conformity also is significant to pupils' engagement, which may indicate that when pupils conform to behavior of others, it can impact pupil engagement by encouraging active involvement in school tasks and activities, depending on the norms of the social group. When students observe their peers actively participating, demonstrating interest, and achieving success, it can inspire and motivate them to become more engaged in their own learning process. Additionally, this social influence is significantly related to pupils' self-regulation. As pupils conform by observing and imitating the behaviors of their peers, and these peers are engage in pro-social or academically focused activities, conformity can promote self-regulation by encouraging students to adopt similar behaviors and strategies. In terms of self-resiliency, it was also found to be significantly related to conformity, which imply that when students conform to social standards, they may feel a stronger feeling of social connection and support, which might boost their self-resilience. When they face obstacles, they are also more likely to obtain support and assistance from peers and others. This social support might help them to be resilient by offering resources and encouragement during difficult times.

With regards to expectation as social influence, it is also significantly related to pupils' academic performance. This implies that if students believe that others have high expectations of them, they will work harder to meet those expectations, which more likely result in increased effort and performance. Likewise, this influence is also significant to pupils' engagement. The feeling that the pupils are capable of academic success or having support from their social surroundings, may increase students' engagement at school. Expectation is significant to self-regulation of the pupils. Teachers, parents, and peers often have high expectations of students' academic performance, demeanor, and engagement in school activities. These expectations can have an impact on students' self-regulation by instilling a sense of responsibility or putting pressure on them to fulfill the expected standards. Students may be driven to regulate their actions and behavior in order to meet these expectations and avoid adverse consequences or disapproval. In terms of self-resiliency, it also has significant relationship to expectation. This may imply that when teachers, parents, and other prominent people in students' lives have high expectations for them, it can promote a sense of confidence in their skills. Positive expectations provide the message that they are capable, competent, and respected. This idea can boost their self-esteem and self-confidence, laying the groundwork for resilience. When faced with adversity, pupils who have high aspirations are more likely to persevere and see setbacks as temporary obstacles rather than insurmountable problems.

The findings also showed that compliance is significantly related to pupils' academic performance. If other people surrounding the pupils were also constantly urging and requesting them to behave properly and study hard, and pupils complied with these, it may lead to better performance and academic achievement. By complying with instructions, completing assignments on time, and following academic standards, students are more likely to perform well in their academic pursuits. As to pupils'

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engagement, it was found out to be significant also to compliance. When students also comply with rules, they may contribute to an organized and ordered school environment, which has a beneficial impact on engagement by instilling a sense of security and stability. Similarly, this social influence is also significant to pupils' self-regulation, which may imply that when students have compliance, it may help them self-regulate by encouraging discipline and adherence to established routines or norms. With regards to self-resilience, it is also significant to compliance which may indicate that when pupils are requested to comply to rules and regulations, they may learn to accept responsibility for their conduct. By fostering a sense of accountability and self-discipline, this may improve their capacity for self-resilience.

Furthermore, obedience as social influence, as significantly related to pupils' academic performance, may imply that when students follow the guidelines, directives, and expectations established and commanded by someone in authority other than their teacher such as their parents/ guardian, elders, school authorities, and others, they are more likely to perform well academically. This may be linked to their capacity for adhering to instructions, meeting deadlines for tasks, and exercising discipline in their academic endeavors. Likewise, the significant relationship found between obedience and engagement may indicate that obedient students tend to be actively involved and invested in their educational experiences. By following instructions and participating in classroom activities, they are more likely to remain focused, attentive, and interested in the learning material. This engagement may lead to deeper understanding, improved retention, and overall academic success. There is also significant relationship between obedience and self-regulation implies that pupils who are obedient to the rules ordered by someone that they look up to, have higher self-control over their actions, feelings, and impulses. They may exhibit self-discipline, adherence to the law, and distraction control. Their ability to maintain focus, withstand temptation, and make deliberate judgments might be helpful for their learning processes. Similarly, with the correlation between obedience and self-resilience, it may imply that students who obey with the orders of other people may be more resilient and adaptable when faced with difficulties or setbacks. By doing so, children gain a sense of responsibility and determination that can help them overcome challenges, bounce back from failures, and persevere in their academic pursuits.

On the whole, the findings show that classroom social dynamics as to social influence is significantly related to supportive learning environment. This may imply that the social influence regarding conformity, expectation, compliance and obedience which are practiced by the pupils may contribute in pupils' academic performance, engagement, self-regulation and self-resiliency, which manifest a supportive learning environment. Social influences may have an impact and play significant roles in shaping a healthy atmosphere for learning. When classroom social dynamics with positive social influence are promoted and nurtured, they contribute in shaping learners' experiences and emotional well-being. Social interactions and relationships within the learning community are conducive in promoting a favorable learning atmosphere, as students feel accepted, included, supported, comfortable asking for help, engaging in discussions, and working together on tasks. It can also promote collaboration, empathy, and motivation, respect, encouragement, and recognition which can boost students' self-worth and confidence in their abilities. Therefore, it is essential for students to have positive social influences in order to more likely develop social skills, succeed academically, model appropriate behavior, feel a sense of belonging, and grow personally. Schools and educators may actively establish a good and welcoming social atmosphere that fosters relationships, promotes empathy and kindness, and generates a climate of support and cooperation among students.

The study findings were supported by the study of Wentzel (2017) which stresses that social relationships are vital to children's growth throughout childhood and adolescence. Children who enjoy interacting positively with others seem to have higher and more dynamic levels of emotional well-being, self-belief, and values for prosocial types of behavior and social interaction than do children who do not have strong social connections. Additionally, they provide a sense of community and recreation, support for problem-solving, emotional security, and a framework for identity formation. In comparison to children with dysfunctional social interactions, children with healthy relationships are more likely to be engaged in their schoolwork and even excel at academic tasks.

LIMITATIONS

It is vital to emphasize that the study had some limitations. The respondents of the study was limited to Grade six pupils of five public elementary schools of San Antonio District, Division of Quezon. This study was strictly confined to the insights of the respondents on their teacher or adviser and was also limited to measuring pupils' academic performance as it used a survey questionnaire. The study's findings and conclusions would only be valid within the confines of its study area and respondents' perceptions and might not be applicable elsewhere.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusions

The findings gathered in the study led to the formulation of the following conclusions:

1. Among the teachers' influence, only referent, expert and reward show significant relationship on supportive learning environment and legitimate influence was only significantly related to pupils' engagement and self-regulation; while coercive influence has no

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significant relationship on supportive learning environment. Hence, the hypothesis stating that there is no significant relationship between supportive learning environment and classroom social dynamics in terms of teachers' influence is partially not sustained.

2. The hypothesis stating that there is no significant relationship between supportive learning environment and classroom social dynamics in terms of social influence is not sustained.

Recommendations

In light of the findings and conclusion of the study, the following recommendations are offered:

1. Schools may implement programs or interventions aimed at continuously upgrading teachers' skills and practices in fostering favorable teacher-student relationships, as well as promoting positive social interactions among students, in order to facilitate an optimal and supportive learning environment for positive classroom social dynamics and enhanced learners' outcomes.
2. Teachers may continue to engage in an inclusive and supportive interactions and connections with their students in order for them to consistently exhibit good conduct and attitudes toward learning.
3. Parents and the community may be mindful of their impact on students' personality and learning. They could be involved in school activities and have open lines of communication between teachers. Regular meetings, feedback sessions, and collaborative efforts to address social dynamics and establish a helpful learning environment can all be part of this.
4. Future researchers may conduct a similar study with larger scope which may involve multi-grade influence as neutral context. They may also explore more on coercive influence of teachers as disciplinary tool for students' academic and behavioral conduct.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The author declares no conflict of interest in the conduct of the study.

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